

Functional Outcome of Intra-Articular Comminuted Distal End Radius Fracture Treated with Ligamentotaxis and Pinning

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Abstract

Background: Distal radius fracture is one of most common fractures seen in clinical practice. Intra-articular comminuted fractures are usually associated with road traffic accidents, fall from height in young patients. In old age groups it is associated with severe osteoporosis due to trivial fall. All intra-articular fractures need good reduction for better functional outcome. The aim of our study is to evaluate the functional outcome of intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fractures treated with Ligamentotaxis and pinning.

Methods: This study was conducted in Orthopaedic Department of Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, Rajasthan between March 2022 to April 2024 on 40 patients with intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fracture, who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. All fractures were managed by ligamentotaxis and pinning and were followed regularly and assessed after three months post-operatively for their final functional outcomes.

Results: Overall, 40 patients of intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fractures treated by ligamentotaxis and pinning. 70% of the study population were males. According to Gartland and Werly score, 50% patients achieved excellent outcomes, 25% had good outcomes, 15% had fair outcomes, and 10% had poor outcome.

Conclusion: Ligamentotaxis and pinning is safe and effective method of treatment for intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fracture. It is also cost-effective method and can be practiced even in small hospital.

Keywords: Intra-articular, distal end radius fractures, ligamentotaxis.

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Introduction

Fractures of the distal end of the radius are the most prevalent upper extremity fractures, constituting approximately one-sixth of all fractures treated in emergency rooms [1]. The fracture is mainly due to road traffic accidents, fall from height in young age and fall with outstretched hand in old age with osteoporosis [2]. Key risk factors include osteoporosis and the tendency to fall onto an outstretched hand [3]. Notably, about 50% of metaphyseal fractures of the distal radius also involve the radiocarpal and/or distal radioulnar joints [4]. Patients with fracture distal end of radius have serious complications more frequently than generally appreciated and failure in management may cause permanent disability [5]. Distal radius fractures disturb the mechanical foundation of the human's most elegant tool, the hand [6]. Restoration of normal alignment and articular congruity after a displaced fracture can be difficult but is essential for a good functional outcome in terms of early wrist motion, improvement in range of motion and grip strength [7].

Treatment approaches for displaced distal radius fractures have evolved significantly over time. His-

torically, closed reduction and immobilization in a plaster cast were standard. Recent advancements have introduced more sophisticated internal and external fixation techniques, such as percutaneous pin fixation, external fixation devices that allow for distraction and palmar translation, low-profile internal fixation plates, arthroscopically assisted reduction, and various bone-grafting methods [8]. These innovations have enhanced fracture stability and outcomes, though debate continues over the optimal method for achieving and maintaining accurate restoration of articular anatomy.

External fixation has gained popularity for managing intra-articular comminuted distal radius fractures due to its minimally invasive nature and its ability to achieve reduction through ligamentotaxis. External fixation using prolonged distraction provides tension through the capsuloligamentous structures across the fracture site. This technique supports bone healing by restoring radial length, volar tilt, and radial angulation to near-normal values. Additionally, it allows for unobstructed elbow-hand movement, enabling patients to perform daily

activities without significant limitations. In our study, we used principle of ligamentotaxis to maintain the fracture fragments in reduction with additional K- wire support.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study involved 40 patients with intra-articular comminuted distal radius fracture treated with ligamentotaxis and pinning. The study was conducted at Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, Rajasthan from March 2022 to April 2024.

Inclusion Criteria: Age between 18 to 60 years, all closed distal radius fracture AO type B and C, Presence of dorsal comminution, Dorsal tilt greater than 10 degrees, Radial shortening greater than 3mm, Presentation within two weeks of trauma, Open fracture grade 1 AO type B2&B3 and C

Exclusion Criteria: AO type A and B1 fractures, Open fractures grade 2 and 3, Bilateral fractures, Previous wrist injuries, Patients with medical contraindications, Pathological fracture, Patients with neurovascular injuries and those who did not give consent for surgery.

Operative Procedure: Upon arrival at outpatient department or emergency department, patients were initially evaluated using the ABCDE Approach (Airway, Breathing, Circulation, Disability, Exposure) and fracture splintage done with an above elbow slab. Detailed patient history taken and associated injuries were recorded. X-rays of the affected wrist and forearm with elbow (AP and Lateral views), along with those of any associated injuries, were taken. After pre-anaesthetic work up, patients underwent surgery using ligamentotaxis and pinning.

After suitable anesthesia, surgical site was prepared and draped. Closed reduction was performed and

confirmed in anteroposterior and lateral view using imaging. Two 1.8 mm K-wires were used to fix the fracture from the radial styloid process under image guidance in a divergent manner, followed by the application of metacarpal pins. A 2mm incision was made over the metaphyseal flare of the second metacarpal, with blunt dissection carried out to avoid injury to the superficial radial nerve and the first dorsal interosseous muscle. A 2.5mm × 100mm Schanz pin was inserted after drilling, with second pin applied distally using the same method. Two radial pins were placed 10-15cm proximal to the radial styloid through 2mm incision, with careful dissection to avoid injury to the radial sensory nerve and extensor tendons. The metacarpal and radial pins were then connected to a distractor, and post-adjustment, X-rays were taken to ensure proper alignment. Pin tract dressing followed.

Patients were encouraged to commence active and passive finger movements from the first day post-operation. A single dose of parenteral antibiotics was administered, followed by oral antibiotics for three days. Pin sites were regularly inspected. Patients were discharged on the third day and scheduled for fortnightly reviews up to six weeks. After confirming union at six to eight weeks, the external fixator and pins were removed, active wrist mobilization commenced post-removal. To assess functional and radiological outcomes patients were reviewed at the end of 12 weeks for final follow up.

Observations and Results

Out of 40 cases, following observations were made and results were analysed radiographically and clinically at 3 months post-operatively, using GARTLAND and WERLEY score.

Table 1: Distribution of Age of Patient

Age(year)	NO.	Percentage
18-30	11	27.5
31-40	11	27.5
41-50	8	20.0
51-60	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0

In our study, nearly 55% cases (22 patients) belong to 18-40 years age group and mean age was 40 years.

Table 2: Distribution of Gender of Patients

Gender	NO.	Percent
Female	12	30.0
Male	28	70.0
Total	40	100.0

Males dominated our study group with 70% (28 patients) of total cases.

Table 3: Distribution of mode of injury of patients

Mode	NO.	Percentage
Road traffic accident	25	62.5
Fall on outstretched hand	15	37.5

In our study, road traffic accidents and fall on the outstretched hand were the common mechanism of injury.

Table 4: Distribution of side of patients

Side	NO.	Percentage
Right	24	60.0
Left	16	40.0
Total	40	100.0

Right sided injuries which are 60% (24 patients), were more common in current study.

Table 5: Distribution of AO Type of Patients

AO Types	NO.	Percentage
23-B2	3	7.5
23-B3	2	5.0
23-C1	8	20.0
23-C2	17	42.5
23-C3	10	25
Total	40	100.0

In current study, in complete particular type the most common type was C2 (42.5%) > C3(25%) > C1 (20%).

The final result of our study:

Table 5: Distribution of result of patients

Result	NO.	Percentage
Excellent	20	50
Good	10	25
Fair	6	15
Poor	4	10
Total	40	100

Complications

In our study, three patients had superficial pin tract infections, three patients developed wrist stiffness, and one patient had pin loosening. We did not

encounter iatrogenic fracture of metaphysis due to pin insertion and iatrogenic neurovascular injury.

Case Illustration

Clinical Photos

Discussion

Management of distal radius fracture has undergone many modifications and more controversies. The effectiveness of ligamentotaxis in counteracting harmful compression forces, which could lead to the displacement of unstable fractures with radial shortening, represents a notable and increasingly attractive development in the treatment of distal radius fractures [9]. The restoration of normal anatomy and preservation of radial length is the most important factor for preservation of function. About 80% of axial loads at the wrist are supported by the distal end of the radius, while the remaining 20% are supported by the triangular fibrocartilage and the distal end of the ulna [10].

Current study evaluates the functional outcome of patients treated with ligamentotaxis and pinning using Gartland and Werley score. 40 patients with intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fracture was employed in the study.

In our study, patients from age group 18 to 60 years old were employed. Mean age of patients was 40 years which was comparable with study of Leung et al. (1989) [11] (mean age 35.6 years), Jain BK et al. (1998) [12] (mean age 37 years), Akmaz et al. (2003) [13] (mean age 39 years) and Aggarwal et al. (2004) [14] (mean age 45 years).

In current study males comprised of 70% (28 patients) and females comprised of 30% (12 patients). High incidence of fractures in males was due to road traffic accidents and their ambulant life. High incidence of fractures in males was also seen

in studies of Leung et al. (1989) [11] (males:73.6%), Jain BK et al. (1998) [12] (males:63.6%).

In current study, road traffic accident found to be the major cause of fracture in 62.5% cases (25 Patients) and 37.5% cases (15 Patients) due to fall on outstretched hand.

In current study, right sided fractures seen in 60% cases (24 Patients) which are found to be more common than left sided fracture, seen in 40% cases (16 Patients), which was probably due to hand dominance.

In current study, all cases belong to either AO type B or C of distal end radius fracture. 35 out of 40 cases had sustained a complete intra-articular fracture i.e., type C fracture accounted for 87.5% which was mainly due to high energy trauma (road traffic accident)

In current study, all patients had good union, the mean time of union was 8 weeks with range of 6 to 10 weeks. Nearly 95% cases (38 patients) had shown good and fair finger movements.

In current study, patients were evaluated by Gartland and Werley score. Overall, 50% cases (20 patients) achieved excellent results, 25% cases (10 patients) achieved good results, 15% cases (6 patients) achieved fair results, and 10% cases (4 patients) achieved poor results. Overall, 75% patients achieved an excellent to good results, which was comparable with other studies.

Table 6: Functional outcome

Study	Excellent to Good (%)	Fair to Poor (%)	Total cases
Cooney WP <i>et al.</i> (1979) [15]	85	15	130
Leung <i>et al.</i> (1989) [11]	80	20	72
Jakim I <i>et al.</i> (1991) [16]	83	17	169
Mannur A <i>et al.</i> (2001) [17]	70	30	20
Our study	75	25	40

Conclusion

Based on the results from similar studies, ligamentotaxis and pinning is a viable surgical option for managing intra-articular comminuted distal end radius fractures. In this study, frame we used cost-effective, easy to apply, tolerated well by the patients. The successful treatment of intra-articular

comminuted fractures of distal end radius is dependent upon the surgeon's ability to restore articular congruity as well as patient's compliance.

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